

HORIZON-RIA

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WHEATBIOME

**Unraveling the potential of the wheat microbiome for the
development of healthier, more sustainable and resilient
wheat-derived food & feed products**

DELIVERABLE D8.1

PROJECT MANAGEMENT GUIDELINES

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
SEN	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Task leader partner for this deliverable: **REQUIMTE**

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides information for the consortium members of the WHEATBIOME project to understand the processes, procedures, roles and obligations of each partner. The processes and procedures are described to ensure an effective and clearly defined methodology for ensuring that the project is delivered as efficiently as possible. This document complements existing project documentation including the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement and should be used in conjunction with these two documents.

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3. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

GA – Grant Agreement

WP – Work Package

EC – European Commission

HE – Horizon Europe

REA - Research Executive Agency

4. INTRODUCTION

The project management plan describes the main project, the organizational, governance, and decision-making structure of the WHEATBIOME project, the project communication strategy, deliverables and document management, reporting, and financial management. It also describes the project risk management processes to handle risks already addressed and possible issues that may arise during the project lifetime. The aim of this document is to provide guidelines and procedures which should be followed within the WHEATBIOME project to ensure that the project is delivered according to the Description of Action in the Grant Agreement. Even though no significant changes to this document are anticipated, the guidance and some sections of this project management plan may be updated based on decisions made by the Steering Committee, through personnel changes or changes to the project's Description of Action, which will necessitate an update to this document.

This plan is based on several key documents including

- The WHEATBIOME Consortium Agreement
- The WHEATBIOME Grant Agreement – GA Number 101084344

5. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The primary project outputs are the deliverables listed in Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A, which will take mainly the form of reports. However, some of the deliverables will be surveys as well prototypes of new food, feed or software tools.

The project is essentially divided into the nine work packages listed below:

- WP1: Study of the factors influencing the microbiomes & attributes of wheat in different areas of Europe
- WP2: Integrative multi-factor evaluation of the influence of soil and plant microbiota on wheat crops
- WP3: New wheat-based microbial-derived food products
- WP4: Validation of novel fermented wheat-based food products
- WP5: Development of cutting-edge fermented poultry feeds
- WP6: Sustainability assessment of the novel wheat-based food and feed fermented production
- WP7: Exploitation, Communication and Dissemination
- WP8: Project Management
- WP9: Ethics requirements

Of these nine work packages, WP1, WP3, WP4, and WP5 will be the most technically oriented and focus on the physical-chemical characterization of soil and wheat (plant and grain), on the characterization of soil and wheat microbiomes, as well as on the the development of new food and feed products, aligned with the screening of specific bioactivities, wheat immunogenicity and the soil-plant-food-host microbial interactions. Additionally, WP2 will focus on developing tools for evaluation and decision-making based on the inputs from the most technical WP.

An analysis of the potential environmental sustainability and economic feasibility will be done within WP6. Additionally, WP7 will focus on maximizing the impact through the Exploitation, Communication, and Dissemination of the project results to the different stakeholders involved in wheat production and transformation.

6. PROJECT ORGANISATION, GOVERNANCE AND DECISION MAKING

The WHEATBIOME organisational structure follows that as set out in the WHEATBIOME Consortium Agreement. The key organisations within the consortium and management structure include:

- General Assembly - the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium;
- Steering Committee - the supervisory body for the advice, ensure delivery of the Project outputs and the achievement of Project outcomes which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly;
- The Coordinator Partner - the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority. The Coordinators shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement. Furthermore, the Coordinators will be the researchers responsible for all aspects of project monitoring, ensuring that all partners are committed and perform the tasks assigned to them, as described in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement, and is also responsible for the communication to the European Commission Project Officer.
- Work Package Leader – responsible for the day-to-day operation, quality and planning of the tasks within the work package.
- Task Leader – responsible for the planning and delivery of the products within their task.

- External Advisor Board - an expert panel nominated group of external senior academics covering expertise in different Project topics, responsible to assist in reviewing project's development and progress, and contributing to Project success.

6.1. PROJECT ORGANISATION, GOVERNANCE AND DECISION MAKING

The governance structure and hierarchy for the management of the WHEATBIOME project is shown in Figure 1. The project governance follows a vertical structure with the General Assembly being the highest decision-making body. The Steering Committee monitors the progress of the project taking input from the Work Package Leaders and may make recommendations for changes to the Description of Action to the General Assembly for authorization.

The reporting structure follows a management-by-exception reporting methodology, whereby any deviations to the task plans should be reported to the Task Leader, if this is expected to have an impact on the content or delivery of any deliverables or milestones within that task, on the work package or on a task within another work package. This should be reported via the Work Package Leader to the Steering Committee who propose mitigation measures to manage this and pass the proposal to the General Assembly for approval (Figure 2). If accepted by the General Assembly, the proposed changes are passed to the EC Project Officer for the next stage of approval.

Figure 1. Governance structure for the WHEATBIOME project.

Figure 2. The hierarchy from Task team to the Steering Committee of the WHEATBIOME project.

6.2. ROLES

The roles of the different project governance groups are defined within the WHEATBIOME Consortium Agreement and below.

6.2.1. GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The General Assembly is the highest decision-making body within WHEATBIOME. By definition, the General Assembly consists of one representative from each consortium partner and is presided over by the Project Coordinator, unless the General Assembly decides otherwise. As a small project with only 13 partners, it was unanimously decided that the General Assembly will be composed of one or two designated representative members from each consortium partner. Any member of the General Assembly may, however, designate a substitute or proxy to attend and vote at any meeting.

The General Assembly is presumed to have the authority to deliberate, negotiate and decide on the matters listed below.

The General Assembly shall be free to formulate proposals and make decisions on its own initiative. In addition, the General Assembly will consider and vote on every proposal made by the Steering Committee. The vote of those Institutions having only one representative member will count double in order to maintain an equal representation among institutions.

The following decisions shall be taken by the General Assembly:

Content, finances and intellectual property rights

- i) Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Funding Authority
- ii) Changes to the Consortium Plan

- iii) Modifications to the Consortium Agreement
- iv) Additions to Annex 3a (Identified Affiliated Entities)

Evolution of the consortium

- i) Entry of a new Party to the consortium and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party
- ii) Withdrawal of a Party from the consortium and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal
- iii) Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium

Agreement or the Grant Agreement

- i) Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
- ii) Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
- iii) Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the consortium and measures relating to this
- iv) Proposal to the Funding Authority for a change of the Coordinator
- v) Proposal to the Funding Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project
- vi) Proposal to the Funding Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement

Appointments

- i) Appointment of the Steering Committee Members and decision on the composition of the Steering Committee

A General Assembly must be held at least twice a year, and additionally can be convened if requested by the Steering Committee, or by 1/3 of the consortium. The General Assembly can be held in person, in a hybrid format, or virtual.

6.2.2. STEERING COMMITTEE

The Steering Committee is responsible for implementing the General Assembly's decisions and proposing to the General Assembly any modifications to the project or consortium plan, including modifications to the Consortium Agreement or Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A, Part B, or Annex 2.

The Steering Committee will include the Coordinators and the WP leaders designated by the General Assembly. The composition of the Steering Committee may be altered, however, by a vote of the General Assembly. The composition of the Steering Committee will be evaluated at the General Assembly, whenever required.

The coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Steering Committee unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

Among the responsibilities of the Steering Committee are:

- Preparing and planning the meetings, proposing resolutions and decisions, and preparing the agenda for the General Assembly.
- Responsibility for the effective execution and implementation of General Assembly resolutions.
- Monitoring the project's effective and efficient implementation.
- Monitoring and providing advice on the budget and financial execution.
- Collecting information on the Project's progress at least once every six months, analyzing that information to assess the Project's compliance with the Consortium Plan, and, if necessary, recommending changes to the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly.
- Assisting the Coordinator in preparing for meetings with the EC agency, as well as preparing relevant data and deliverables.
- Advise the General Assembly on methods for reorganizing responsibilities and budget.

Steering Committee meetings will also be attended by the Project Manager who will be responsible for ensuring that the meeting runs on time while taking notes and managing possible future risks.

6.2.3. PROJECT COORDINATOR

The role of the Coordinators is to act as an intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority EC and to carry out all tasks outlined in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. The Coordinator is primarily responsible for the administrative and financial aspects of the project.

Specifically, the Coordinator is responsible for:

- Monitoring the Parties' compliance with their obligations;
- Maintaining a current and accessible list of Members, their contacts, and other relevant contact information;
- Collecting, evaluating for consistency, and submitting to EC reports, other deliverables (such as financial statements and related certifications), as well as, specifically requested documents;

- Transmitting project-related documents and information to all other interested parties;
- Administering the Funding Authority's financial contribution and completing financial duties;
- Providing, upon request, official copies or originals of documents in the Coordinator's sole possession when such copies or originals are required for the Parties to present claims;
- If one or more of the Parties is late in submitting a project deliverable, the Coordinator may still submit to the Funding Authority on time all other parties' project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement.

The Coordinator is supported by a Project Manager who will take responsibility for the day-to-day project and financial aspects. The Project Manager will take responsibility for the project and administrative aspects of the WHEATBIOME project and together with the appointed Financial Support representative, will coordinate the financial reporting of the project and the distributions of pre-finance and final payments to the project partners.

The Project Manager role will include:

- Collating and reporting project progress.
- Raising any concerns, risks or issues arising to the General Assembly and Steering Committee.
- Preparing the agenda for the General Assembly and Steering Committee for approval by the Project Coordinator and each executive board respectively.
- Uploading the deliverables to the Participant Portal.
- Co-ordinating the financial and project reporting to REA.
- Prepare consortium-wide communications and calling notices to Consortium meetings, the Steering Committee meetings and General Assemblies.
- Prepare the final minutes for Consortium Meetings, the Steering Committee meetings and General Assemblies.

6.2.4. WORK PACKAGE LEADERS

Work package leaders are responsible for the programme within their work package. The work package leader role includes:

- Ensuring that the tasks and deliverables within their work package are delivered on time and to the required quality criteria and according to the budget provided.

- Identifying and reporting risks and deviations within their work package to the Project Coordinators and Project Manager.

6.2.5. TASK LEADERS

The task leaders are responsible for the work within their task, ensuring that tasks are delivered on time and to budget, reporting any deviations from the work plan to the work package leader, for further escalation if necessary to the project board.

6.3. ORGANIZATIONAL MEETINGS AND PROCEDURES

6.3.1. FREQUENCY OF CONSORTIUM MEETINGS

The constituted meeting frequencies for the General Assembly and Steering Committee are detailed below:

Table 1. Periodicity of Consortium Meetings

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	At least twice a year	At any time upon written request of the Executive Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly
Steering Committee	At least every 3 months	At any time upon written request of any Member of the Steering Committee

It is recommended that the work packages also meet at least every 2 months, and between the physical meetings teleconference calls or video conference calls to ensure that decisions can be made, and progress monitored.

To reduce travel costs, the WHEATBIOME project aims to combine as many of the meetings as possible and hold whole consortium meetings once a year, which will include Steering Committee meetings, followed by General Assembly meetings.

Meeting participants should be appropriate to the topics being discussed. To ensure that meetings are an effective use of time and budget, only those participants whose work will be impacted by the outcomes from the meeting, or who have input to be reported to the meeting should attend and invite lists should be minimized.

6.3.2. NOTICE OF A MEETING

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall give notice in writing of a meeting to each member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Table 2. Timeframe of Consortium Meetings notice

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Steering Committee	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

Any meeting will be called using a Calling Notice, for the whole Consortium Meeting, Steering Committee and General Assemblies. The calling notice sets the time and date of the meeting, identifies the attendees who should participate in the meeting, the aims and objectives of the meeting, the agenda and reference to any supporting documentation which should be read prior to the meeting taking place. If there is a physical meeting the calling notice should also contain the meeting location, and recommended travel arrangements and accommodation. The Calling Notices shall be issued by the Project Manager. The Calling Notice also acts as an authorization to travel by the Project Coordinator.

Any Work Package meetings or meetings between partners which require travel also require a calling notice to be issued which can be obtained by contacting the Project Manager or Project Coordinator. If no travel is required, the calling notice may be issued by the Work Package or Task Leader as appropriate.

6.3.3. SENDING THE AGENDA

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each member of that Consortium Body a first version of the written agenda by the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Table 3. Timeframe to send Agenda for Consortium Meetings

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	21 calendar days	10 calendar days
Steering Committee	7 calendar days	3 calendar days

However, good practice dictates that as much notice as possible should be given. For in-person Consortium meetings, it is recommended that at least one calendar month of notice should be given to enable participants to plan their time and obtain the best deals for travel. The agenda of the meeting should be included in the calling notice.

For virtual Work Package meetings, the agenda should be issued 7 calendar days before the meeting and any changes to the agenda should be sent at least 3 days before the meeting.

6.3.4. ADDING ITEMS TO THE AGENDA

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any Member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to all of the other members of that Consortium Body up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Table 4. Timeframe of to add Agenda items

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	14 calendar days	7 calendar days
Steering Committee	2 calendar days	1 calendar day

Whenever necessary, the members of a Consortium Body present or represented can, during a meeting, unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

6.3.5. RUNNING OF MEETINGS

Within each meeting a chairperson should be assigned as well as someone to track record the minutes and actions of the meeting. For Steering Committee Meetings and General Assemblies, the chairperson will be the project coordinator assisted by the project manager. For Work Package and Task meetings, the meeting should be facilitated by the work package or task leader respectively, who may choose to collect the minutes of the meeting themselves or assign someone else for this task.

In the case that chairperson is not available, the consortium meeting may appoint another chair.

6.3.6. DECISIONS

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if the coordinator circulates to all members of the Consortium Body a written document which is then agreed upon by the defined majority of all Members of the Consortium Body. Such a document shall include the deadline for responses.

Meetings of each Consortium Body may also be held by teleconference or other telecommunication means.

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the Minutes has been accepted.

6.3.7. MINUTES OF THE MEETING

Minutes of the meeting should be made available 15 days after the end of the meeting. The minutes will reflect any issues discussed within the meeting, conclusions and actions agreed. The minutes should be circulated to all parties concerned for comments or approval, upon issuing the minutes a deadline should be set for the return of comments and in the absence of comments beyond the deadline the minutes are deemed to be approved. The minutes of meetings will be stored on the Teams Platform in the appropriate folder for the meeting:

- Minutes of General Assemblies and Steering Committee Meetings will be stored under WP8/meetings.
- Minutes from Work Package and Task meetings should be stored in the folder for the appropriate Work Package.

A template of the minutes is stored on the Teams Platform (General folder » Templates subfolder).

6.3.8. ABSENCES

If any member of the Steering Committee, Work Package leader or Task Leader expects to be absent from work or unable to fulfill their duties for a significant period of time this should be reported to the Project Coordinators and a nominated contact/replacement should be assigned to cover their duties.

The project manager will produce a list of deliverable due dates, the review periods for each deliverable and a list of participants involved in the deliverable review process. If any participant is expecting to be absent during one of these review periods, which would result in them being unable to fulfill their duties, they should notify the Project Coordinators in order to allow them to assign a replacement.

7. PROJECT COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

7.1. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

7.1.1. TEAMS PLATFORM

REQUIMTE, the coordinator institution, has created a workspace on Teams Platform dedicated to the WHEATBIOME project. The platform is administered and maintained by REQUIMTE and is accessible to all Consortium partners and members.

The Teams platform provides:

- Shared document space for all official project documentation, calling notices, agenda, minutes, templates and working documents and final deliverables. The Teams platform provides document version control and user configuration controls.
- Directories for the contact details of personnel working on the project.
- Organizational tools for the planning, communication and scheduling of meetings.
- Logos to be used in communication.
- A channel for general chat within the whole consortium and specific channels for each WP to improve information interchange in real time.
- A channel for following the financial issues with reports for the planning activities and funding needed and also reports on the financial management after ending the tasks (see Section 8.1.2). Information regarding the personal costs and hiring as well as the information on acquired equipment and rationale will be also included.

7.1.2. CONTACT LISTS

A contact list has been created and is available as an excel worksheet (a standard file format). The contact list is regularly updated by the Project Manager and includes email addresses of all participants of the consortium. The contact list can also include the contact details for alternative forms of communication in case the participants want to share additional contact ways.

The contact list is organized by consortium bodies – general assembly and steering committee - and also by work packages. This is intended to prevent the proliferation of emails and broadcasting to the whole consortium. Where possible consortium members should only email the contacts to whom the email is relevant and global emails should be minimized.

7.1.3. EMAIL

Email is expected to be the primary form of communication within the WHEATBIOME project. An official email account (wheatbiome@requimte.pt) was created to ensure professional communication, consistency, and centralized information dissemination among members and stakeholders. It also guarantees security, compliance, and long-term sustainability of the consortium's activities. This email account will be used mostly by the project management team to efficiently communicate with the consortium.

For ease of identifying WHEATBIOME relevant emails, we recommend that all email subjects should begin with “WHEATBIOME” and have the following structure to allow recipients to quickly identify emails that are relevant to them:

Structure: WHEATBIOME [ADMIN] [ALL] [WPx] TOPIC

Some examples of the application of this structure are presented below:

- 1) an email regarding a Work Package 1 teleconference could have an email subject line:

WHEATBIOME | WP1 | Teleconference 2023-09-20

- 2) an email about a particular deliverable may have the email subject line:

WHEATBIOME | WP2 | D2.3-Participant input required

- 3) administrative matters should have ADMIN in the subject line:

WHEATBIOME | ADMIN | Financial details required

- 4) broadcast messages to the whole consortium ALL should be included in the subject line:

WHEATBIOME| ALL | Calling Notice for General Assembly

7.1.4. TELECONFERENCING

Teleconferencing is recommended as a means of cost-effective communication and an alternative to certain short meetings. The most effective teleconferences are those that are well structured, with clear aims and objectives.

Teleconferences are especially useful for:

- Talking a group through a document or presentation;
- Briefly discussing technical or management issues;
- Assigning tasks to participants;
- Making decisions requiring urgent actions;

To ensure that teleconferences are as efficient as possible, it is recommended that:

- The meeting is limited to a small group of participants;
- The meeting has a clear aim and objective and when possible limits the meeting to individuals presenting or reporting back to the group, confirming that they will take future actions or agreeing on predefined points.

Teleconferences should be minuted and organized in the same way as any other meeting, with an agenda issued prior to the meeting, a list of participants recorded as well as a list of actions produced.

7.2. EXTERNAL COMMUNICATIONS AND DISSEMINATION

The strategy for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of the project will be detailed in Deliverable D7.1. For management of External Communication and Dissemination, Contactica (CTA) will compile the reports of the partners with the performed activities. Every three months, an Excel file will be sent to all partners for them to fill with the communication and dissemination activities performed. If an event or activity is foreseen in the near future, CTA should be informed in order to promote the activity. If this doesn't happen, the performed activity should be included in the Excel report.

Moreover, a document with communication general guidelines for WHEATBIOME was also prepared by CTA and is available for consultation by all participants on Teams platform, on the documents folder in WP7 channel.

8. DELIVERABLES

The project deliverables will mainly be in the form of reports which are uploaded to EC Funding & Tenders Portal as evidence of the work carried out. A report will be produced to demonstrate the work carried out regardless of being a food prototype, software, a database, document or publicity material, an event or a website.

The Grant Agreement Annex1 Part A - List of deliverables (page 25), documents each deliverable, the due date and the dissemination level of that deliverable. Each deliverable will be subjected to a review process.

8.1. STRUCTURE OF DELIVERABLES

Each deliverable should follow a set structure as set out in the templates (WHEATBIOME Teams platform » General folder » Templates subfolder) of:

- Cover: including Deliverable number and title, due date, WP relation, leader beneficiary and partners contributions.
- A table regarding the status and versions of the document, highlighting the changes performed between versions.
- Executive Summary – a brief summary of the key points of the main document.
- Table of Contents.
- Abbreviations and Acronyms.
- Introduction – an outline of the aims and objectives of the deliverable and where it fits in the context of the WHEATBIOME project. The introduction should also explain the interdependencies related to this deliverable, whether this work is drawing on earlier tasks and deliverables and what other tasks will use this deliverable as input or for structuring their work.
- Main body of the report – this section will explain the task that was carried out and the results generated and illustrate the technical and scientific progress made within the task.
- Conclusions – these sections should be a summary of the major outputs of the deliverable and the implications of the results on other parts of the project or the impact on that the results will have for the end-users and the science community. The conclusions should also highlight the deficiencies in the work carried out and where future improvements or further work should be directed.
- References.
- Annexes – Annexes of data or further information not suitable for the main body of the report either due to its detailed nature or separated for confidentiality purposes.

8.2. TRACKING OF DELIVERABLES

Deliverables will be tracked by the Project Manager, identifying deliverables due in the near future, the deadlines for each deliverable, follow-up actions and the names of the persons producing and reviewing.

8.3. DISSEMINATION LEVEL OF DELIVERABLES

During the proposal stage it was agreed that the WHEATBIOME deliverables would have a Sensitive (SEN) or a Public (PU) dissemination level meaning that depending on the deliverable they will be made available only to the Consortium Body and the granting authorities or to anyone, respectively. This ensures that when possible the results of the project can reach the largest audience possible. However, particular tasks may need to use data or information which is confidential or commercially valuable, in which case a subset or example of such data or information will be presented in the sensitive deliverable.

8.4. MILESTONES

The WHEATBIOME milestones are not subject to the same review process as the deliverables and are mainly a project management tool to ensure that progress is being made. Each milestone will be assessed against a quality criteria by the project management team and progress or completion status will be reported to the Steering Committee as an indicator of progress and uploaded on the EC Funding & Tenders Portal by the Project Manager.

Project milestones are listed in the Grant Agreement Annex1 Part A - List of milestones (pg 41).

8.5. REVIEW PROCESS

A review process and timescales for the preparation and submission of deliverables were agreed by all partners (Figure 3) Writing and preparing the first draft of the deliverable is the responsibility of task leader(s), assisted by the WP leader(s). The first version of the deliverable should be ready for revision by the Steering Committee members 31 calendar days before its submission deadline. The Steering Committee will have 15 days to review and comment possible changes. After this revision, the task leader(s) has 7 calendar days to prepare the final version of the deliverable, which should be sent to the Project Manager no later than 7 days before the submission deadline. The Project Manager will ensure that the documents are formatted and structured correctly, properly named and labeled before uploading the deliverable to the EC Funding & Tenders Portal. Project Manager will notify the task leaders and WP leaders involved in the preparation of each deliverable 60 calendar days before the submission deadline, but the responsibility for complying with the delivery

sub folders for Final Deliverables, Working reports and Documents and Meetings related documents (Table 5).

Table 5. Organization of WHEATBIOME Teams Platform

Top level folder	Sub folder	Explanation
General	Contracts	Final version of the grant agreement, consortium agreement, amendments
	Documents in preparation	Documents in preparation by all consortium, such as internal reports and meeting agendas
	Financial Plan	
	Project planning templates	MS Project version of project Gantt charts and other Project Management documents
	Reporting	Internal periodic reports and documents for periodic reviews
	Templates	Templates for deliverables, calling notices, meeting minutes and presentation templates
	Images	Partner Logos Project logo Bank of useful images which can be used in publications and presentations
	General presentations	Presentations of the project
	Project Flyers and Newsletter	Communication and Dissemination material
	Other publications	Papers and poster, news articles
WP1	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice
WP2	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice
WP3	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice
WP4	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice
WP5	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice
WP6	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice
WP7	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice
WP8	Final Deliverables	
	Working reports and documents	Working space for draft documents
	Meetings	Minutes of meetings, presentations and calling notice

Whenever necessary, other subfolders can be created to help organize relevant documentation and content produced during the project execution.

9.2. DOCUMENT TEMPLATES

Document templates have been produced which use a standard format including defined styles, page layout and content structure. These templates are available on the Teams Platform site under General Folder » Templates subfolder.

Templates have been produced for:

- Deliverables (MS Word format)
- Meeting Calling Notices (MS Word format)
- Meeting Minutes (MS Word format)
- Presentations (MS Powerpoint format)

All official project documents should use these templates. These templates may be updated as the project progresses and may be redesigned to fit with the design style of the project logo. Therefore, consortium partners should download the most up to date version from the Teams Platform.

9.3. FILE FORMATS

File format and compatibility is important for the exchange of documents between different partners using different systems.

The following file formats should be used:

- Word processor documents – Microsoft Office WORD version 2007 or higher (.doc or .docx formats)
- Spreadsheet documents – Microsoft Office EXCEL version 2007 or higher (.xls or .xlsx formats)
- Presentations – Microsoft Office POWERPOINT version 2007 or higher (.ppt or .pptx formats)
- Promotional materials (flyers, newsletters) and/or other non-editable project documents – PDF format
- For compressed files – ZIP format

- Bitmap image files – JPEG or PNG formats
- Vector graphic files – EMF or SVG formats
- Video files - MP4 (H.264 + ACC)

9.4. DOCUMENT CODING

Each document should use a structured file name and use the same structure for the document reference. This method of document coding produces a unique reference for all WHEATBIOME documents stored on the platform.

The document reference should be structured using the following:

WHEATBIOME-WP[WP_NUMBER]-[DOCUMENT_TYPE_AND_REFERENCE]- [DISSEMINATION LEVEL]-v[VERSION NUMBER]-[STATUS]

Examples of this structure are given below for the different document types:

1) Deliverables

Structure: WHEATBIOME-WPx-Dx.x-DISSEMINATION LEVEL-vx.x-STATUS

Eg. WHEATBIOME-WP6-D6.5-PU-v0.1-DRAFT

2) Calling notices

Structure: WHEATBIOME-MEETING TYPE-DISSEMINATION LEVEL-Meeting dates-vx.x-STATUS

Eg. WHEATBIOME-GA1-SEN-SEN-2015-06-15-v0.1-DRAFT

3) Meeting minutes

Structure: WHEATBIOME-WPx-MINUTES-DISSEMINATION LEVEL-Meeting dates-vx.xSTATUS

Eg. WHEATBIOME-GA1-MINUTES-SEN-2015-06-15-v1.0-FINAL

10. REPORTING AND REVIEWS

10.1. EC/REA REPORT AND REVIEWS

The Research Executive Agency (REA) on behalf of the European Commission (EC) monitors progress and achievements of the project through:

- Periodic reporting
- Evaluation of project deliverables and achieved milestones
- Project reviews

These forms of assessment present the evidence that the project is progressing, should continue and that the Consortium has completed its duty as set out in the Grant Agreement and is eligible for the EC payment.

In addition to reporting to REA, the WHEATBIOME Project Management Team will also carry out interim internal reports for monitoring progress of the project and allocation of resources with the assistance of the Steering Committee.

10.1.1. PERIODIC REPORTING

The WHEATBIOME project has three project reporting periods as defined in table 6.

Table 6. Reporting periods and payments.

Reporting				Payment
Report No	Reporting Period	Type	Deadline	Type
1	M1-M18 (Jan2023-Jun2024)	Periodic Report	M20 (Aug 2024)	Interim Payment
2	M19-M36 (Jul2024-Dec2025)	Periodic Report	M38 (Feb2026)	Interim Payment
3	M37-M48 (Jan2026-Dec2026)	Final Report	M50 (Feb2027)	Final Payment

The periodic reporting includes a technical report and a financial part and are integrated with the interim and final payments.

To ensure a timely delivery of the reports, the Project Manager will prepare the templates and notify the partners of their duties and where they should contribute to the report at least 2 calendar months before the end of the reporting period. The Project Manager will then ask that each participant completes their reporting 30 calendar days after the end of the reporting period, which will allow the Project Manager a further 30 calendar days to compile the report and to ensure that the report is presented to sufficient quality. It is expected that all partners will contribute to the report, reporting on their participation with Work Package leaders and also reporting on the progress made within their Work Package.

The Period 1 and 2 mid-project reviews will include the following documents:

- A publishable summary of the WHEATBIOME project.

- Deliverables which were due within the reporting period according to the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A.
- Periodic Activity Report on the results and achievements of the project over the corresponding reporting period, including the progress made on tasks, deliverables and attainment of milestones. And if any deviations have occurred from the Description of Action in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, an explanation justifying the differences. The Periodic Activity Report will also include a plan for the exploitation and dissemination of the results
- Issues related to the action implementation and the economic and societal impact.
- Form C financial statements of each partner.
- Explanation of the use of resources.

The final end of project review will include the same documents as mid-project reviews, but applied to the whole project and in addition it will include:

- A publishable summary report of all of the results, conclusions and the impact of the project, the benefits to end-users and society.
- A final technical report.
- An update to the exploitation plan for the implementation and dissemination of the products of the project.
- Certificate of the Financial Statement (CFS) provided by the auditor for each partner if their total requested funding exceeds €350k.

10.2. INTERNAL REPORTING

At every mid-point between the reporting periods for REA the WHEATBIOME project will include an internal review. The internal reviews will be carried out at M12 (December 2023) and M24 (December 2024).

10.2.1. INTERNAL REPORTS

The internal reports aim to help preparing the Periodic Reports for REA and be an internal project management tool to review the progress towards the aims and obligations of the period. It will also be used to monitor the project resources.

The templates used in the internal reports will be similar to those used in the Periodic Report for REA.

The internal report is expected to include:

- A description of activities and progress towards completion of tasks, deliverables and milestones.
- Dissemination activities carried out, including peer reviewed publications, articles, presentations, conferences, news items.
- An estimation from each partner of the budget and time consumed.

The internal review will be prepared by the Project Management Team with input from all partners. This internal report will then be circulated within the consortium and presented to the Project Steering Committee as part of the Internal Project Review.

10.2.2. INTERNAL PROJECT REVIEW

The internal project review will be carried out by the Steering Committee after the completion of the internal project report. The Steering Committee will allow the WP leaders to present their activities to the whole consortium, ensuring cohesion between the different work streams. The internal project review will also allow the Steering Committee to review progress and decide whether there is need to take action and, if necessary, the Steering Committee will propose to the General Assembly changes to the budget or to the Description of the Action.

10.3. FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

This information on financial management is based on the WHEATBIOME Grant Agreement No 101084344 (article 21 and article 22) and the [EU Funding & Tenders Online Manual](#) – Section 3.3. Grant Management. All clearances carried out respect the agreement of approved candidates and in accordance with the legislation in force for national and European projects. Project physical file, supporting documents (expenses and original payments) at the institution's headquarters.

10.4. FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

The financial statement of costs (Form C) should be completed by each partner and is submitted via the Participant Portal at the end of each Reporting Period (M18, M36 and M48 of the project). The financial statements should be in compliance with each partner internal accounting practices. However, each partner should check that:

- The WHEATBIOME Project costs are correctly identified within their accounts.

- Only eligible costs are claimed for and can be separated from non-eligible costs.
- All records (timesheets, invoices, receipts etc) are properly stored and are retrievable in the case of an audit.

Actual Costs must be:

- Actually incurred by the beneficiary.
- Incurred during the action.
- Indicated in the estimated budget set out in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement.
- Incurred in connection with the action as described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and necessary for its implementation.
- Identifiable and verifiable – recorded in the beneficiary’s accounts in accordance with the accounting standards applicable in the country where the beneficiary is established and with the beneficiary’s usual cost practices.
- Reasonable, justified and must comply with the principle of sound financial management.
- Must comply with the applicable national law, labour and social security.

Ineligible costs include:

- Costs related to return on capital.
- Debt and debt service charges.
- Provisions for future losses or debts.
- Interest owed.
- Doubtful debts.
- Currency exchange losses.
- Bank costs charged by the beneficiary’s bank for transfers for the commission/agency.
- Excessive or reckless expenditure.
- Deductible VAT.
- Costs incurred during suspension of the actions.

10.4.1. PERSONNEL COSTS

Eligible Personnel Costs are:

- Related to personnel working for the beneficiary under an employment contract (or equivalent appointing act) and assigned to the action.
- Limited to salaries (including during parental leave), social security contribution, taxes and other costs included in the remuneration, if they arise from national law or the employment

contract.

Timesheets are no longer required for personnel if 100% of their time is spent working on this project for the full reporting period. However, for any organization to which this applies, they will need to submit a declaration to confirm that they have completed 100% of their time on the WHEATBIOME project.

For the purpose of reporting we will still need to report which Work Package staff have been working on and a breakdown of how much time has been spent on each Work Package.

For all other staff it is compulsory for them to complete a timesheet. Timesheets should be completed on at least a monthly basis and must record the time down to a Work Package level.

Timesheets should also be authorized by a line manager or another senior manager. If a company's existing timesheet system can meet these requirements then this can be used for recording the time for the WHEATBIOME project. Templates for timesheets are available on the EC Funding & Tenders Portal at [Reference Documents](#) in the tab Time declaration.

10.4.2. PREPARATION OF FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

The Project Management Team is responsible for collecting, checking and compiling the project's Financial Statements. The Project Management Team will also inform the Project Coordinator of any delays or difficulties encountered in the production and compilation of the financial statements including any delay in receiving information from a partner or a major discrepancy and where necessary propose a contingency plan.

Financial statements will aim to be submitted with other reporting documents to REA within 60 calendars after the end of each reporting period.

To ensure a timely response, the following procedure will be applied for the preparation of the Financial Statements:

- Upload at M6, M18, M36, and M48 in the WHEATBIOME Teams Platform, General/Financial Plan folder, a Financial Plan focusing on how the budget allocated to each partner is estimated to be used for the next year.
- Two months before the end of the Reporting Period the Project Management Team will issue clarification notes for each partner on what is required from them and when.
- 30 calendar days after the end of the Reporting Period the partners should have completed their Financial Statements on the Participant Portal.
- The Project Manager will compile all financial statements and CFS and check them for compliance

- In the case of a partner not submitting their Financial Statements in time, the Project Coordinator can decide whether or not to include that partner's financial statement in the submission to REA. Excluding a partner's financial statement will result in them having to wait until the next reporting period for further funds, but would allow the payments to all other partners to be delivered on-schedule and avoid the delay of payment to majority of the consortium
- The Project Management Team will compile the Financial Statements and the Certificates and send them to the Coordinator at least 2 days prior to the deadline.

10.4.3. CERTIFICATE OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT

The Financial Report consists of the structured individual and consolidated Financial Statements (retrieved from the Grant Management System). In addition, most programmes require either a detailed cost reporting table (excel table) or the use of resources report (online wizard) and, for payments above a certain thresholds, a certificate on the financial statements (CFS). The CFS is a report produced by an independent auditor (or, for public bodies, public officer) using the template available on Portal Reference Documents. Its purpose is to give assurance to the Granting Authority about the regularity of the costs claimed.

The thresholds depend on the EU programme and type of action (see call conditions on the Topic page). For the MFF 2021-2027, there is usually a single threshold of EUR € 350 000 requested EU contribution. The CFS should be submitted no later than 60 days after the end of the final reporting period. A model for the financial statements is provided within the Grant Agreement - Annex 4.

10.5. PAYMENT HANDLING

10.5.1. PAYMENTS FROM THE EC

The EC will transfer the grant to the coordinator bank account. The coordinator is then responsible for distributing the money to the other beneficiaries on the project.

The maximum total EC financial contribution for WHEATBIOME is fixed at 5,060,547.91€.

Pre-financing

This is made at the start of the project, usually within 30 days of the EC signing the Grant Agreement.

The pre-finance payment made to the coordinator was limited to 50% of the Maximum EC Financial Contribution (as described in Data Sheet, point 4.2). The pre-finance payment will be distributed to the partners with each receiving 45% of their Maximum EC Financial Contribution, after withdrawing 5% of the total amount relative to the contribution to the Mutual Insurance Mechanism.

Interim Payments

These are made after each periodic report is submitted and accepted by the EC. The interim payment will be limited to 90% of the Maximum EC Financial Contribution (as described in Data Sheet, point 4.2).

Final Payment

This is made at the end of the project once the EC has accepted all deliverables and reports and will include any remaining part of the eligible costs and contributions defined to the implementation of the project.

Mutual Insurance Mechanism

The contribution to the Mutual Insurance Mechanism is a percentage of the budget that the EC withholds of each partner's budget at the start of the project, which for the WHEATBIOME was set out to 5% (as described in Data Sheet, point 4.2). If no financial negative balance or any other financial issues are depicted at the end of the project, this contribution is paid out by the EC with the final payment.

Distribution of funds to partners

The EC financial contribution is received by the Project Coordinator on behalf of the consortium, split by the number of reporting periods. The Project Coordinator will then distribute the EC financial contribution to each partner without unjustified delay according to the rules set out in the Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement.

Subsequent payments will be based on the validation of the deliverables and the cost statements submitted to EC and potentially dependent upon any budget changes proposed by the Project Steering Committee and approved by the General Assembly and the ERA/EC Project Officer.

In order to properly follow-up the financial management and considering the structure of the consortium:

Those Institutions who have different research groups/departments/faculties with complementary expertise but well differentiated tasks within the whole project must present the financial management in detail, disaggregating the costs spent for each task and research group.

11. PROJECT RISKS MANAGEMENT

11.1. ISSUE REGISTER

The “Issue Register” is a log of any issue which arises during the course of the project and will be maintained by the Project Manager. The Issue Register will collate any issue as it arises, issues will then be analyzed and escalated or dealt with accordingly. An issue could be anything which is of concern to a partner, Work Package Leader or the Steering Committee, this could be deviations from the project plan, identification of new risks or just concerns.

For example it may be an issue such as Partner X is not responding to emails, this may be a precursor to larger problems which may impact on the work programme, therefore, as an issue is raised it may cause a trigger which causes a new risk to be identified and added to the risk register and contingency plans to be devised or it may result in the Steering Committee proposing actions are taken.

It is the role of the Project Manager to sort and assign the actions to items raised on the Issue Register and ensure that the actions are followed up. However, it is the role of all consortium members to raise issues and present them to the Project Manager.

11.2. RISK MANAGEMENT AND RISK REGISTER

A risk management strategy is required to ensure that the impact from any negative deviation from the Description of Action is minimized. The risk management process consists of 5 key steps:

1. Identify and assess risk
2. Analyze critical risks
3. Development of contingency plans
4. Implement contingency plans
5. Update risk register and follow up of contingency plans

A list of risks was identified during the grant preparation stage (table 7). This risk register will be maintained and updated throughout the project, each WP leader is expected to identify any new risks occurring within or affecting their Work Package and the Steering Committee identify any global risks which may have an impact across the Work Packages. Each risk will be assessed by the Steering Committee for its criticality to the overall plan of work and normal risk assessment techniques such as a likelihood/severity matrix can be

used for assessing the potential risk impact and therefore the requirement for the implementation of a contingency plan.

The risk register will be reviewed by the Steering Committee at each board meeting, any new risks identified, updated, assessed and contingency plans created if necessary. The Steering Committee will also assess whether the likelihood or severity of existing risks have changed and create or update the contingency plans. If a contingency plan results in a change to GA Annex 1 a proposal for the change should be proposed by the Steering Committee for approval by the General Assembly.

Any contingency plan developed and implemented as a result of the risk management process will be subject to reporting and periodic progress updates to the project management team and to the Steering Committee.

Table 7. Critical risks & risk management strategy

Risk number	Description	Work Package No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
R1	High variability in soil/plant microbiome	WP1	Samples will be collected during 3 consecutive years to reduce variability due to unplanned factors. Thorough analysis of soils and plant samples will allow to further categorise wheat microbiomes and reduce variables in the analysis. Only healthy crops will be selected to avoid the unpredictable effect of pests on soil and plant microbiomes composition and interaction.
R2	Difficulty to identify main factors affecting wheat microbiomes and crop quality in open-cultured crops	WP2	Wheat sample fields are organized in case studies to reduce the inconsistency in some factors (i.e., soil type, climate conditions, agronomic habits) and SOPs will minimize variability. The selected biotic/abiotic factors will be validated under controlled conditions (greenhouse) during 2 successive years.
R3	Difficulties associated to fermented food product quality and stability	WP3	The screening of several fermentation tests (POCs), and the constant inspection of nutritional quality and safety (i.e., xenobiotics) will provide evidence for modulation of quality and stability. If technical difficulties to prepare the fermentation samples are encountered, alternative methods during fermentation or processing will be investigated.
R4	Innovative cellular models mimicking human microbiomes require too much optimization before testing novel fermented foods	WP4	The interaction of novel fermented foods with human microbiota will be first assessed by the novel cellular models designed for WHEATBIOME, but if optimization is above project execution timing, already recognised cellular models will be used instead.

R5	Low consumers acceptance of the palatability of the novel developed food product	WP4	The in vitro analysis of taste will be a first filter and to optimize food production. Then, consumer's perception and sensory assays will determine acceptable food products by consumers before validation of food pre-prototype in clinical trials.
R6	Novel wheat-base fermented foods do not show health improvement in healthy participants	WP4	Clinical trials will be carried out on healthy volunteers, so no prejudicial effect of the novel food products is an encouraging result and further clinical trials could be designed to prove the beneficial effect on non-healthy groups of individuals.
R7	Difficulties in the scaling-up the fermentation of feed production	WP5	Scaling up will be progressive (1.5L, 16L and 50L). If optimization to large-scale (50L) does not produce stable and good quality fermented feed, several batches of 16L fermentation will be produced and mixed for studies on poultry.
R8	Low impact of novel fermented feed on poultry	WP5	The 3 best performing fermentation POCs with top feed nutritional characteristics will be frequently evaluated. If no sufficient effects are observed before half-study time, animal tests will stop and other POCs will be assessed instead.
R9	Lack of reliable sustainability data on novel microbiomes in the current databases	WP6	New datasets with results derived from the project's studies and available literature will be created and uploaded to current databases to enrich the info on novel microbiomes sustainability.
R10	Communication activities do not engage enough audiences	WP7	Cross-posting strategies will be followed in order to engage with the public in any digital or presential activity. Visual and physical communication and educational material will be in all the languages of the participant countries (and English).
R11	IP sharing problems between partners, and project foreground protection risked	WP8	The CA was signed between partners to minimise the risk of IPR conflicts. Foreground IP will be divided and assigned to only one partner, who will take the full responsibility for protection.
R12	Stakeholders (food system actors and consumers), do not engage with survey studies, educational activities, sensory assay or clinical trials	WP4, WP2, WP7	Activity leaders have a successful track record (see Section 3.2) and clear information and close contact with researchers will reinforce the commitment of participants. Studies will be done in sets so any withdrawal could be neutralized in the next group.
R13	Financial risks (funding delays, overspending)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8	Adequate funding, audited oversight of institutional financial management; expenditure monitoring and early initial site visits to assess full project budgeting will be carried out.
R14	Impossibility of carrying out face-to-face activities (training, field trips, sensory assays, ...) due to COVID or other unexpected situations	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8	Online activities (e.g., video-meeting, interactive/visual material) will be scheduled instead. For sensory assays and clinical trials, minimum-contact SOPs will be established (i.e., food samples will be delivered home). For lab research, teams will be divided to limit contact and

			overtake duties in case of disease/quarantine.
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11.3. LESSONS LEARNT LOG

A lessons log will also be maintained by the Project Manager, to record lessons generated out of the “Issues Register ” and any other lessons from the project. The lessons log will categorize the lessons for their significance to different parties and the stage in future projects at which the lesson log should be reviewed. The WHEATBIOME project’s lessons log will be available to all of the consortium members and to REA to ensure that lessons learnt in this project may be applied to future projects.

12. CONCLUSION

The Project Management Plan presented in the document provides a guide to be used by the Project Manager and the consortium partners to ensure an understanding of the roles and responsibilities of each member of the consortium in delivering the WHEATBIOME project through efficient and well managed processes. This document should be used by partners to complement the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Further guidelines may also be found on the [EU Funding & Tenders Online Manual](#).

If any item in this document is ambiguous, or further assistance or advice is required then please contact the Project Coordinators and/or the Project Manager.